

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Software_03: prep3_b.f95

Kobzos, Laszlo

zehu.kola.ci@gmail.com

1. Abstract

This description is closely related to an **older article** of the same main title [1], reading this article will make it easier to understand more. It mostly discusses the working principle of our ECG Feature Extraction (FEX) "**progr1-123**" program. This program system does not extract the features (FEX) automatically, but with frequent operator interaction. Between the steps, he draws the diagram necessary for further decisions, and based on this, the operator determines the next step of the program.

In our two previous descriptions, we dealt with the operation and use of the first preparation program "**prep**" [8], and in the second description, the operation and use of the second preparation program, the "**oneper**" [9] program.

In the following descriptions, unlike this, we are no longer discussing a preparatory program. But this was also written in **Fortran**, just like the previous programs, so we will write about it now. This **prep3_b.f95** program is related to the Octave [4] part of the FEX3 program system. The program deals with setting some new parameters of the function described in section {[1]4. Method, 4.1. *The approximation function*}. "In general, approximations require an initial set of parameters" {[1]4.9. *Tools for approximating a wave*}. "Multiplying the numerator or denominator of an existing approximate function, or both, by new factor(s) is called *expansion*." Here we are now dealing with the expansion of the denominator.

- we will explain the structure of the "**adat_file-×_u.txt**" and "**rel_par-××.txt**" files.
- what kind of expansions the program deals with.
- we explain which parameters we take from the command line.
- we describe the modification of the "**adat_file-×_u.txt**" file: we copy the "**adat_file-×_u.txt**" file into an auxiliary file by replacing a few important lines in between, and then overwrite the original with this file.

This "**2. We repeat...**" section below was copied here verbatim from the description of the "**oneper**" program [9].

Note: In the *.txt format files, auxiliary comments are often included at the end of the lines used by the programs, as well as after the lines. (These comments are not used by programs.)

2. We repeat and supplement some information from the mentioned above article [1]:

The **Fortran** we use {[1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*} and its environment:

64 bits processor, Windows 7 Professional with Service Pack 1
GNU Fortran (GCC) 4.8.1 with 0.6.2-mingw32-beta-20131004-1

This compiler is not Fortran IV or Fortran 66: "The GNU Fortran compiler supports the Fortran 77, 90 and 95 standards completely, parts of the Fortran 2003 and Fortran 2008 standards, and several vendor extensions" [3]. In addition to these modern improvements, we can use older subroutines, such as those in MINPACK, without changing the source code!

Our records uploaded in the topic of the main title can be accessed by the following search:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.name%3A%20%22Kobzos%2C%20Laszlo%22&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

Since this program system **does not automatically calculate the features** (FEX), but with frequent operator interaction, we create **diagrams** for them, using **MS_EXCEL** or **GNU Octave** [4]. The **transfer of information** between the parts of our program system usually takes place in text files. So are the above programs. In these text files, we used a **decimal point** (for GNU Octave) or a **decimal comma** (for MS_EXCEL). Any text editor can be used to transform them, replacing all commas with points or vice versa.

The source code of our programs is usually provided with many **comments** for their use and possible modifications. The comments are in Hungarian. The same goes for text outputs. We hope that the English language **program descriptions** and **user guides** will be of sufficient help to understand our programs.

We use two types of character encoding:

- For Windows text files and comments: Windows-1250
- For Windows Command Prompt (~DOS) files: OEM 852

If we use Notepad++ : Encoding | Character sets | Central European | ...

The source of the ECG data used { [1] 4.5 *Data* } :

Our ECG data comes from the **PhysioNet database** [2]. From this database, 549 **anonymised** ECG data of 290 individuals can be accessed by selecting PTB. In addition to the signals, the "PTB Diagnostic ECG Database" contains other data, as well (such as: age, sex and diagnosis of the individuals, ...). Signals are sampled at 1 kHz (i.e. 1 sample per 1 millisecond), and a 1mV signal corresponds to a quantisation level of 2000. Although our method is independent of the lead system, we have mainly investigated 3 leads of the **Frank system** (vx, vy and vz; sometimes only x, y and z). Using Dower or inverse-Dower matrix transformations, the data of the conventional 12-lead system can be calculated from the Frank lead system data, and vice versa [5, 6].

The original ECG signals: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13026/C28C71> License: Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0

We do not deal with cases of **arhythmia**, because these signs belong to the "should consult a cardiologist" category.

A commonly used method to extract the feature data (FEX, Feature Extraction): "A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions." For approximation, the rational function was written in the root factor form { [1] 4.1. *The approximation function* }. The roots of the denominator and the numerator are called poles and zeros, respectively.

Identifying the periods used { [1] 5. *Results*, first paragraph } :

The signals tested are denoted as follows: s.... = serial number, p... = patient number. For example "s0025_p005". If we want to be more precise about the location within the record, we also indicate the lead and the location of the QRS. For example "s0025_p005, vz, 7009".

The coordinate system used { [1] 4.6. *The coordinate system used* } :

The **x-axis** (t-axis) of a period of a lead was determined with a method usually **used in cardiology**. That is, in the signal-free part before the P wave of the period, we identify a location where the noise is limited, or filter out the noise by "looking", and we mark the starting point of the baseline. The other point of the baseline is similarly determined at the next P wave. The line passing through these two points is called the **baseline**.

The time value of the maximum point of the signal energy (proportional to the square of the voltage) was chosen as the **origin**. This point is always within the QRS-complex. In more detail: In the case of a **Frank lead** system, since it is orthogonal in space, we used the Pythagorean Theorem to determine the curve of the voltage vector length from the vx, vy, vz leads. Its maximum indicates the maximum activity of the electrical signal of the heart. Because of the noise on the leads, we instead cut the curve at 95% of the maximum voltage vector and choose the middle point between the two intersections as the time value of the origin. Since this does not usually coincide with the location of the sampling point, we round to the nearest location.

If we do not use a Frank lead system, but a 12-lead system, then the location of the origin can be determined in the same way using the (nearly perpendicular) V6, II and $-0.5 \times V2$ leads [7].

Addendum to this: In programs, the last character of the variable name is often **A** or **R**. This usually means **Absolute** or **Relative**. For example: i_P1_loc**A**. For the ECG signal downloaded from the database, the character **A** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the signal, while **R** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the selected period (P, QRS and T). In those programs that deal with only one period, **A** indicates the distance from the beginning of the period, while **R** indicates the (signed) distance from the QRS wave.

We wrote at the beginning of all our programs written in Fortran (.f95) that we do not use automatic type declaration (**implicit none**). But **usually** the first letter of **INTEGER** variables is "I, J, K, L, M, or N". The **LOGICAL** variables **usually** start with "log_" and **CHARACTER** variables with "ch".

The number of parameters of the above-mentioned function is often listed in programs, data files and diagrams. For example, variable names: ch_fajt12, i_P_fajt1, i_P_fajt2, i_fajt2. For example in figures: P35 "stands for wave P, 3 is the number of parameters of the numerator (including the leading coefficient **d**), while 5 is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) of the denominator. Thus, the number of parameters of the approximation is $3 + 2 \times 5 = 13$."

The two six-character numbers in the data files and in the figures are the timestamp. This 2×6 digit number (yymmdd hhmss) means "year month day hour minute second".

In our figures containing a single period:

- On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the 1×1 mm square of ECG signals (so-called "small square") this corresponds to 40 points (40 ms) \times 200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings. This 40 points \times 200 points grid - enlarged according to the size of the figure - shown on all our diagrams containing ECG signals.

- Drawing the imaginary values of the roots on the same diagram as the ECG signals we multiplied them by 50, 70, 7 and 50 for the P, QRS, T and Ta waves, respectively (for old ECG signals: 50, 100, 10, -).

- In the figures, the poles are marked with **x** and the zeros with **o**.
- In the figures, only one of the two conjugated complex roots was shown, namely always the one falling towards the momentary value of the signal.

3. Program Description

This **prep3_b.f95** program is related to the Octave [4] part of the FEX3 program system. The program deals with setting some new parameters of the function described in section {[1]4. Method, 4.1. *The approximation function*}. "In general, approximations require an initial set of parameters" {[1]4.9. *Tools for approximating a wave*}. "Multiplying the numerator or denominator of an existing approximate function, or both, by new factor(s) is called *expansion*." Here we are now dealing with the expansion of the denominator.

The two main data files of the approximation program (**progr1-123**) are the ECG signal contained in **sam-oneper.txt**, and the coefficients of the approximate rational fraction function (+additional parameters) contained in **adat_file-x_u.txt** (where: x = x, y or z).

3.1. Block structure of parameter files

The **adat_file...** consists of as many blocks as there are waves we are approximating. That is, it first consists of a block, which we change until the rational function - of the known form - closely approximates the first wave of the period. Then, after the final result of the first wave approximation, we insert the second block (with the initial approximation of the second wave) into the file. Waves are denoted by numbers in the programs and in the **adat_file...** . Each block begins with these wave-numbers, followed by other auxiliary parameters, and ends with the line of rational function parameters (parameter-line).

Finally, a wave-number of 0.

The number of wave-numbers and the number of rows of blocks in the program just discussed (**prep3_b.f95**) can be followed in the INTEGER FUNCTION `i_tart()` section.

So initially:

1 P wave----

7-1 row auxiliary parameter (the 1 must be subtracted because the 7 would jump to the next wave-number row)

Parameters of the P wave function approximation

0

If we consider the P wave approximation to be adequate:

1 P wave----

7-1 row auxiliary parameter

Final parameters of the P wave function approximation

3 T wave----

9-1 line auxiliary parameter

Parameters of the T wave function approximation

0

If there is also a Ta wave in the period (if P-Q is not isoelectric), then the wave-number of the first block is 5, and 9-1 rows are auxiliary parameters, and then lastly the parameters of the Ta approximation. We will not deal with the Ta wave in this program, but - if it exists - we will skip its lines.

The entire block structure can be easily followed in the attached "**AUXX\adat_file-ures.txt**" file (template file).

3.2. Structure of the function parameter line of the parameter file (parameter-line)

A parameter-line consists of a string of numbers in the format '(1X,E10.4)'. Its structure consists of four parts. These are the parameters of the rational fractional function mentioned above {[1]4. Method, 4.1. The approximation function}. With the notations there, in order: **d** is the leading coefficient, **c** is the location of the zero of the first-degree polynomial of the numerator, **g_n** and **a_n** are two parameters each of the second-degree polynomials of the numerator, and then **h_m** and **b_m** are two parameters each of the second-degree polynomials of the denominator.

The **d** and **c** occupy one place each. The quadratic terms are filled in from left to right.

In the program, the variable **i_par_nb_max** is the maximum number of all parameters of the current wave.

In the program, the variable **i_nz_max** is the max. number of quadratic parameters of the numerator (zeros).

In the program, the variable **i_np_max** is the maximum number of quadratic parameters of the denominator (poles).

These three variables, knowing the wave-number, receive values in the "SUBROUTINE koz_par_data" section, from the "INCLUDE **koz_par.f95**" file at the beginning of the program.

The second line of the block (hereinafter referred to as "fajt line" or "fajt12 line") contains 2 values, related to the actual number of parameters {[1]5. Results, second paragraph}. The first character is the number of parameters of the numerator (here the first is the **d**). From an even number of real zeros, **we combine each pair** into a single quadratic factor.

The second number is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) of the denominator.

The files contain these two numbers as two **hexadecimal** characters.

3.3. Structure of the "rel_par- \times .txt" and "tol-ig.txt" files

After each step of the approximation program (**progr1-123**), it copies the parameters of the approximation result, i.e. one line, to the end of the text file "**rel_par- \times .txt**". Here the first $\times = 1, 2, 3$ are leads vx, vy or vz respectively; the second $\times = 1, 2..$ i.e. the P, QRS.. wave-numbers respectively. At the end of the lines, some additional data is added: the above-mentioned "fajt12"; then the standard deviation of the approximation, and finally the timestamp {[1]5. Results, second paragraph}.

The "**tol-ig.txt**" file contains the locations of the beginning and end of the P, QRS and T waves in 3 lines. These values are relative (**R**) locations to the QRS. As we wrote [9]: "In those programs that deal with **only one period**, **A** (absolute) indicates the distance from the beginning of the period, while **R** (relative) indicates the (signed) distance from the QRS wave".

Input UNITS:

command line parameters

101 adat_file-×_u.txt

103 rel_par-××.txt

105 tol-ig.txt

107 Octa\PQRST_1.txt, 1 character, usually the wave number is stored here (or some special values: 0,8,9)

Output UNITS:

screen

122 adat_aux.txt auxiliary file, we write the lines here, and then finally copy this back to **adat_file-×_u.txt**

INCLUDE "koz_par.f95" See its description above.

01~ ~~~ chapter

We read the value of the "XYZ1" environment variable (leads-number, see section 3.3) into the variable n_xyz.

And in the jwave_k variable, put the wave-number from the "Octa\PQRST_1.txt" file. (if 1, then the P wave, ...)

The output to the screen is not visible now because the program's calling string contains >NULL. So we won't discuss these now.

We read the first command line parameter into the **i_fl_ru** variable.

If **i_fl_ru** = 1, only the approximation result parameters will be copied back from the end of the "**rel_par-××.txt**" file to the parameter-line.

If **i_fl_ru** = 2, then it happens as if **i_fl_ru** = 1 and then "A **general quadratic expansion factor** is used as the new factor of the denominator" {[1]4.9. *Tools for approximating a wave, 3e. Poles:*}.

If **i_fl_ru** = 4, then in this step a **second** new **general quadratic expansion factor** is applied to the previous parameters of the approximation {[1]4.11. *Problems and their practical solutions; fourth paragraph: ...only slightly better...* }.

We read the second command line parameter into the **i_fl_sz** variable.

If **i_fl_sz** = 0, then the numerator parameters are also transferred from the "**rel_par-××.txt**" file to the parameter-line.

If **i_fl_sz** = 1 the numerator parameters are not transferred from the "**rel_par-××.txt**" file, i.e. the previous numerator parameters remains.

Note: this does not make sense if **i_fl_ru** = 4, since in this case the numerator parameters always remain.

We have already written about the **koz_par_adatok** subroutine in section 3.3 above.

02~ ~~~ chapter

In the **adat_file- \times _u.txt** file, we go down to the `jwave_k` block.

We set the value of the variable `i_sor_cs1`.

If the value of `fajt12` does not need to be changed, the variable `i_sor_cs1` remains 0.

If it changes, the value of the variable `i_sor_cs1` is the number of the line in the file that contains `fajt12`.

The content of the `fajt12` line is contained in the `ch_fajta` string.

In the case of the parameter-line, the line number is contained in the `i_sor_cs2` variable, while its content is contained in the `ch_par` string. The contents of the `ch_par` string are: the parameters (1X,E10.4) at the beginning, and a comment at the end.

03~ ~~~ chapter

Rearrangement: we convert the parameters into values and put them in the `par_adatf` array, and only the comment part is placed at the beginning of the `ch_par` string.

04~ ~~~ chapter

Reading the last line of "**rel_par- $\times\times$.txt**" file (the results of the last approximation) into the `ch_rel` string.

Then we convert the parameters into values and put them in the `par_adatf` array.

05~ ~~~ chapter

If `i_fl_ru = 1`, i.e. there is no expansion, then we skip this part.

If `i_fl_ru = 4`, i.e. we expand the parameter-line, we transfer it to the `par_adatf(:)==> par_relpf(:)` array (this is just a programming simplification).

If we have reached the maximum number of pole pairs, there is no expansion.

If there is an expansion, the second hexadecimal number of `fajt12` is increased by 1.

This value is used to we calculate the position in which the expansion will be placed (`i_seg`).

We read the location of the beginning and end of the current wave from the "**tol-ig.txt**" file.

Then, based on the description in section {1]4.9. *Tools for approximating a wave; 3e. Poles*}, we calculate the expansion parameters (position value, shape value and enter them in the appropriate places (`i_seg` position and the following)).

06~ ~~~ chapter

If `i_fl_sz = 1`, then the value of the numerator is not transferred from the "**rel_par- $\times\times$.txt**" file, the one in the previous parameter-line remains. Actually, we

transfer it, but overwrite it with the originals: Since the values are stored in the `par_relpf(:)` array, we copy the entire numerator part here. Specifically, we do not copy the value of `par_relpf(1)`, because we have already set it in the *05~ ~~~ chapter* section.

We copy the `par_relpf(:)` array into the `par_adatf(:)` array.

07~ ~~~ chapter

Since you cannot write to the middle of a file, we create the new **adat_file-×_u.txt** file line by line.

That is, we read a complete line from the file **adat_file-×_u.txt** and copy it to a file "AUX\adat_aux.txt". We continue this in loop until the end of the file. Meanwhile, we keep track of which line we are on:

If we reach line `i_sor_cs1`, we write the new type line instead of the read line.

Similarly, when we reach the line `i_sor_cs2`, we write the new parameter-line.

End of run.

08~ ~~~ chapter

"INTEGER FUNCTION `i_tart()`" its task is to return how many lines in the file "**adat_file-×_u.txt**" belong to the given wave.

09~ ~~~ chapter

A SUBROUTINE `ARG_OLV (i_ksorsz)` its task is to read the command line parameters (`i_fl_ru`, `i_fl_sz`).

End of program.

4. User Guide

The preparation of this program can be described very briefly, because all the preparations have already been done by the other programs. There is no need for console input.

5. References

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